

Three species and two genera of darkling beetles (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) new to the Bulgarian fauna

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Abstract: *Cnemeplatia atropos* A. Costa, 1847, *Lyphia tetraphylla* (Fairmaire, 1856) and *Uloma rufa* (Piller & Mitterpacher, 1783) as well as the genera *Cnemeplatia* Costa, 1847 and *Lyphia* Mulsant & Rey, 1859 are reported for the first time in Bulgaria. Pictures of the specimens and a map illustrating distribution of these species in the country are provided.

Keywords: Bulgaria, *Cnemeplatia atropos*, *Lyphia tetraphylla*, species occurrence, *Uloma rufa*

Introduction

Cnemeplatia Costa, 1847 (Tenebrionidae: Pimeliinae: Cnemeplatiini) is a small genus and consists of 11 primarily Palaearctic species, although some of them also occur in the Afrotropical and Indo-Malayan biogeographic realms (Kaszab, 1966; Ferrer et al., 2009; Schawaller et al., 2014; Merkl et al., 2015; Ferrer, 2016; Iwan et al., 2020). Three of the species are presented in Europe – *Cnemeplatia atropos* Costa, 1847, *Cnemeplatia rufa* Tournier, 1874 and *Cnemeplatia theryi* Kaszab, 1938 (Ferrer et al., 2009). *Cnemeplatia theryi* is endemic to Southern Spain; *C. rufa* is known from the Western Mediterranean – Algeria, Morocco, Portugal, Spain and Tunisia (Ferrer et al., 2009); *C. atropos* is more widespread – Southern and part of Central Europe, Northern Africa, Middle East, Caucasus, Southern Russia and Central Asia (Abdurakhmanov & Nabozhenko, 2011; Iwan et al., 2020).

Cnemeplatia atropos appears to be rare across much of its range (Scupola, 1982; Lencina Gutiérrez et al., 2007; Lillig et al., 2012b) although the records

might be sporadic due to its cryptic lifestyle combined with the small size (2–3 mm in length), specific colour and body coated with soil particles, as these features allow it to blend seamlessly with the surrounding environment (Lencina Gutiérrez et al., 2007; Soldati, 2010; Merkl & Szénási, 2018). This species is terricolous (Bouget et al., 2019) and occurs in places with either wet (Ponel et al., 2013) or dry soil (Merkl & Szénási, 2018). Despite of being considered halophilic it also inhabits non-saline areas (Nabozhenko & Chigray, 2014). Occasionally, it can be found at the roots of *Olea europaea* L. (Kiesenwetter, 1861), *Ceratonia siliqua* L. (Mifsud & Scupola, 1998) and species of the genus *Asphodelus* (Ponel et al., 2013) as well as under mosses (Costa, 1847), in anthills (Kaszab, 1957; Merkl & Szénási, 2018) and decomposing plant matter (e.g. oak, poplar and carob leaf litter, wood crumbs and compost piles) (Sahlberg, 1903, 1913; Scupola, 1982; Koch, 1989; Lillig et al., 2012b; Bouget et al., 2019). Furthermore, *Eucalyptus* sp. (Mifsud & Scupola, 1998 Lillig et al., 2012b) and species of the genus *Olea* (Bouget et al., 2019) have been reported as hosts for this facultative

saproxylic species. *Cnemeplatia atropos* is nocturnal and attracted to light (Kaszab, 1969; Novák, 2014).

The genus *Lyphia* Mulsant & Rey, 1859 (Tenebrionidae: Tenebrioninae: Triboliini) contains 24 valid species spread worldwide except for the Neotropical and Antarctic biogeographic realms (Kaszab, 1974; Ferrer, 2007; Matthews & Bouchard, 2008; Schawaller, 2017; Iwan et al., 2020). Only two of the species are presented in Europe – *Lyphia angusta* (Lucas, 1846) and *Lyphia tetraphylla* (Fairmaire, 1856) (Iwan et al., 2020). *Lyphia angusta* is recorded from France (Corsica), Spain (south continental part of the country, Mallorca, Canary Islands), Algeria (Ferrer, 2007) and Morocco (Mouna et al., 2011). *Lyphia tetraphylla* has wider distribution range than the previous species: Central Europe (Horion, 1956; Černý, 1992), Southern Europe, Anatolia, Levant, Eastern and Southern United States (Bousquet et al., 2018; Iwan et al., 2020; GBIF, 2026b).

Lyphia tetraphylla is considered rare across its range and has patchy distribution in Europe (Aliquò et al., 2006; Aliquò & Soldati, 2010; Lillig et al., 2012a; Soldati et al., 2024). This saproxylic beetle prefers small dead branches or trunks (diameter < 10 cm) of species of the genera *Ficus*, *Quercus* and *Vitis* or sometimes *Ceratonia* (Bouget et al., 2019) as well as *Pistacia lentiscus* L. (Yus Ramos & Coello García, 2008) and persimmon tree (Blackman & Stage, 1924). According to Novák (2014) it can also be found in the fruiting bodies of the polypore fungus *Laetiporus sulphureus* (Bull.) Murrill (1920). It is thought that *L. tetraphylla* feeds on some bostrichid beetles but remains unclear if it actively predaes them or scavenges their remains; however, the species was found in the galleries of *Xylopertha praeusta* (Germar, 1817), *Sinoxylon sexdentatum* (Olivier, 1790), *Amphicerus bimaculatus* (Olivier, 1790) and *Xyloperthella picea* (Olivier, 1790) (Perris, 1877; Saint-Albin, 1960; Español, 1971; Aliquò et al., 2006; Soldati, 2007; Aliquò & Soldati, 2010; Soldati et al., 2024). Liberto & Leo (2006) also found several specimens on branches of *Quercus* sp. infested by the following buprestid and cerambycid beetles: *Coraebus fasciatus* (Villers, 1789), *Agrilus angustulus* (Illiger, 1803) and *Phymatodes alni* (Linnaeus, 1767). *Lyphia tetraphylla* overwinters as adult (Saint-Albin, 1960). It is nocturnal and attracted to light (Lillig et al., 2012b).

Uloma Dejean, 1821 (Tenebrionidae: Tenebrioninae: Ulomini) is a speciose genus that comprises around 250 species (Kaszab, 1982) and its

representatives are found in all biogeographic realms except Antarctica (Merkl & Ando, 2018). This genus is particularly diverse in the tropics and subtropics (Nabozhenko & Ivanov, 2024), especially in the Indo-Malayan and Australian realms, excluding the arid regions (Kaszab, 1982; Stebnicka, 1991). The highest diversity of *Uloma* species in the Palearctic occurs in its southeastern parts (Himalayas, South and East China as well as Japan) near the border with the Indo-Malayan realm. Only four species are recorded from Europe (Iwan et al., 2020): *Uloma culinaris* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Uloma rufa* (Piller & Mitterpacher, 1783), *Uloma picea* Küster, 1846 and *Uloma cypraea* Kraatz, 1873. The last two species have limited distribution: *U. picea* – Croatia; *U. cypraea* – Greece, Cyprus, the Asian part of Turkey (Iwan et al., 2020) and Syria (GBIF, 2026c). The other two have a wider range: *U. culinaris* – almost entire Europe (from Spain, Central England and Norway to the Urals in Russia as well as Caucasus) and northern Iran (Iwan et al., 2020; Clayhills, 2020; Smets et al., 2021; Bacal & Buşmachiu, 2022; Nabozhenko & Ivanov, 2024); *U. rufa* – a trans-Palearctic species known from Spain and Morocco in the west to the Primorsky Krai in Russia in the east (Alekseev, 2008; Efimov, 2008; Medvedev & Sundukov, 2009; Iwan et al., 2020).

Despite being widespread, *Uloma rufa* typically exists in low densities (Bouget et al., 2019). This sapro-xylophagous beetle lives in coniferous or mixed forests and prefers but is not confined to coniferous hosts: primary – species of the genus *Pinus*; secondary – species of the genera *Abies*, *Picea*, *Betula*, *Robinia*, *Quercus* and *Fagus* (Wenzel, 2002; Cherney, 2005; Nikitsky, 2016; Bouget et al., 2019). It may also supplement its diet with wood-decay fungi (Iwan et al., 2012; Tsinkevich & Prishchepchik, 2014) and has been found in decaying wood infested with white- and brown-rot fungi (Wenzel, 2002; Schmidl et al., 2005; Alekseev, 2008; Tsinkevich & Prishchepchik, 2014) as well as in red-rotten wood (Koch, 1989; Schawaller, 2015). *Uloma rufa* often colonises deadwood in open or semi-open forest areas (Nikitsky et al., 1996; Wikars, 2014; Nikitsky, 2016; Ulfsson & Swenson, 2018; Karjalainen, 2020), generally prefers large-sized deadwood (diameter > 40 cm) (Bouget et al., 2019) but can also be found in sawdust piles (Karjalainen, 2020). The flight period is from May–June to August (Nikitsky et al., 1996; Nikitsky, 2016) when beetles can also be spotted flying in forest meadows (Efimov, 2008). Its life cycle

Fig. 1. *Cnemeplatia atropos*, habitus, dorsal view. Scale line: 500 μ m.

lasts two years, both adults and larvae can overwinter, pupates in wood (Nikitsky et al., 1996; Nikitsky, 2016) and new adults emerge in summer (Perris, 1857). This species is nocturnal and attracted to light (Ulfsson & Swenson, 2018).

Methods

Material was collected in the period 2008–2025. Specimens were caught by hand or using a light “tower” device with 160W mercury-vapour lamp and 8W actinic tube lamp. Exemplars were subsequently fixed in a mixture of 70 % ethanol and acetic acid, an absolute ethanol or in cork with ethyl acetate. Genitalia were extracted, macerated in KOH and stained in chlorazol black.

The specimens were photographed with a Canon EOS R50 camera with Laowa 25mm f/2.8 2.5-5X Ultra Macro and Laowa Aurogon FF 10-50X NA0.5 Supermicro APO lenses attached to a WeMacro rail. Genitalia of *L. tetraphylla* were photographed with a

Canon EOS 2000D attached to a Zeiss Jena Amplival compound microscope. Genitalia of *U. rufa* were photographed with the same camera attached to Zeiss Stemi 2000-C stereo microscope. Different focal planes were stacked with Helicon focus Pro 8.3.11.

Distribution map was created using ArcGIS 10.9.1. software. Background layers were downloaded from the following scientific and free websites: SRTM 90m Digital Elevation Database v4.1 (Jarvis et al., 2008), Black Sea bathymetry (EMODnet Bathymetry Consortium, 2024), country borders (Sevdari & Marmullaku, 2023), rivers and lakes (EEA / CLMS, 2020). All raster and vector layers were processed with ArcGIS 10.9.1. software to account for the map scale (1: 3600000) and visualisation requirements.

Collected specimens were deposited in the zoological collections of Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski, Bulgaria (BFUS), Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (IBER-BAS) and National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (NMNHS-BAS).

Results and discussion

Cnemeplatia atropos Costa, 1847 (Fig. 1)
= *Autocera anticipes* Wollaston, 1857

Material: Bulgaria, Burgas Lowland, Sredets County, Suhodol Vill., N42.440697° E27.084138°, 126 m a.s.l., 7.VI.2024, 1 ex. (BFUS-TEN000076), in funnel-shaped antlion pit of *Euroleon nostras* (Geoffroy, 1785), leg. V. Vassilev.

Distribution: Afghanistan, Algeria, Azerbaijan (including Nakhichevan), Bulgaria (new country record, see Fig. 2), Croatia, Cyprus, Egypt, France (including Corsica), Greece (including Cephalonia, Corfu, Crete, Naxos, Zakynthos), Hungary, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Italy (including Capri, Sicily), Kazakhstan, Malta, Morocco, Portugal (Madeira Archipelago), Romania, Russia (Dagestan, Volgograd Oblast), Saudi Arabia, Spain (including Canary Islands), Sudan, Syria, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkey (European and Asian territories), Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Yemen (Faust, 1877; Porta, 1934; Kühnelt, 1965; Ferrer et al., 2009; Abdurakhmanov & Nabozhenko, 2011; Schawaller et al., 2014; Iwan et al., 2020; Nabozhenko et al., 2021).

Fig. 2. Distribution of *Cnemeplatia atropos* (green circle), *Lyphia tetrphylla* (blue circle) and *Uloma rufa* (red circles) in Bulgaria.

Notes: *Cnemeplatia atropos* was initially reported from Bulgaria on social media [iNaturalist and Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF, 2026a)] without mentioning that it is a new country record. This shows that information published on the citizen science platforms should be approached with caution since its accuracy is not guaranteed. Besides that, the following records of *C. atropos* are not listed in the “Distribution” section as they need further confirmation. Nabozhenko et al. (2021) do not support the Armenian record (Abdurakhmanov & Nabozhenko, 2011) due to the lack of material, so the authors excluded the species from the checklist of the country’s darkling beetles. The records from Gibraltar and mainland Portugal are erroneous since *C. rufa* was misidentified as *C. atropos* (López-Colón et al., 2021). Gambian record presented on the website of the Biological Museum at Lund University (MZLU, 2026) also requires confirmation.

Liberto & Leo (2023) quoted Ferrari’s (2021) bachelor’s thesis incorrectly by reporting the species from the Greek island of Gavdos instead of Crete. Additionally, we didn’t find any data that substantiates the records from Sardinia, San Marino and Western Sahara published by Abdurakhmanov & Nabozhenko (2014). In conclusion, proper species identification and thorough bibliographic search are equally important for determining current distribution of any taxon.

Lyphia tetrphylla (Fairmaire, 1856) (Fig. 3)
 = *Bius tetrphyllus* Fairmaire, 1856
 = *Lyphia ficicola* Mulsant & Rey, 1859
 = *Hypophloeus rugosa* Dury, 1902

Material: Bulgaria, Strandzha Mt., Black Sea Coast, NW of Sinemorets Vill., near Veleka river mouth,

Fig. 3. *Lyphia tetraphylla*, male: (A) inner sternite VIII, outer side view; (B) spiculum gastrale, ventral view; (C) aedeagus, lateral view; (D) aedeagus, ventral view; (E) habitus, dorsal view. Scale lines: (A–D) 250 µm; (E) 1 mm.

N42.064791° E27.971140°, 4 m a.s.l., 14–15. VIII.2010, 1 ♂ (BFUS-TEN000077), at light, leg. O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov.

Distribution: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria (new country record, see Fig. 2), Croatia (including Krk, Mljet, Pag), Cyprus, France (including Corsica), Greece, Israel, Italy (including Sardinia, Sicily), Malta, Montenegro, Slovakia, Spain (including Balearic Islands), Turkey (Asian territories), United States of America (District of Columbia, Florida, Georgia, Kentucky, Maryland, Ohio, Oklahoma) (Müller, 1920–1921; Aliquò et al., 2006; Ferrer, 2007; Denux & Zagatti, 2010; Novák, 2014; Lillig et al., 2012b; Bousquet et al., 2018; Iwan et al., 2020; Kazilas, 2021; GBIF, 2026b).

Notes: Although some authors state that *Lyphia tetraphylla* is of Nearctic origin and was introduced to Europe (Horion, 1956; Černý, 1992; Šefrová & Laštůvka, 2005; Löbl et al., 2008; Novák, 2014; Iwan et al., 2020) the genus itself originated in the Old World (Kaszab, 1979; Soldati et al., 2024). This

species is adventive to North America (Bousquet et al., 2018; Bouget et al., 2019; Soldati et al., 2024) and remains the only member of the genus that occurs in the Nearctic realm (Aalbu et al., 2002; Bousquet et al., 2018). In this regard, the reports suggesting that it is a cosmopolitan species (Leng, 1920; Swezey, 1942; Aalbu et al., 2002) or invasive to some European countries (e.g. Montenegro or Greece) (Bulatović et al., 2016; Korakaki et al., 2021) are incorrect. This species was recorded from the Czech Republic back in 1934 (Horion, 1956) but according to Novák (2014) it went extinct in the country. It was also listed as endangered in the Red List of Italian saproxylic beetles (Audisio et al., 2014). Swezey (1942) reported *L. tetraphylla* from Hawaii but also noted that the specimens probably belong to the species *L. angusta*, as indicated by Dr F. E. Blaisdell. Finally, the Kenyan record (Kahuthia et al., 2019) requires confirmation as the identification of the specimens was based on keys to genus level.

Fig. 4. *Uloma rufa*, male: (A) inner sternite VIII, outer side view; (B) spiculum gastrale, ventral view; (C) aedeagus, lateral view; (D) aedeagus, ventral view; (E) habitus, dorsal view. Scale lines: (A–D) 250 μ m; (E) 1 mm.

Uloma (Uloma) rufa (Piller & Mitterpacher, 1783)

(Fig. 4)

= *Tenebrio rufus* Piller & Mitterpacher, 1783

= *Uloma perroudi* Mulsant & Guillebeau, 1855

Material: Bulgaria, Pirin Mts, Kresna Gorge, SW of Stara Kresna Vill., Sheytan dere Place, N41.759981° E23.158233°, 288 m a.s.l., 11–12.VI.2008, 1 ♂ (BFUS-TEN000078), at light, leg. O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov; Central Predbalkan, Vasilyovska planina Mt., NE of Vasilyovo Vill., Kozi dol Place, 5–7.V.2015, N42.8953° E24.3817°, 769 m a.s.l., 5 ex. (NMNHS-BAS), leg. R. Bekchiev & K. Smets; W Rhodopes Mts, Slaveyno Vill., approx. N41.64° E24.86°, 1290 m a.s.l., 18–25.VII.2016, 1 ♂ (BFUS-TEN000079), leg. A. Palov; Kazanlak Valley, Kazanlak, N42.634351° E25.404707°, 464 m a.s.l., 26.III.2025, 1 ♂ (BFUS-TEN000080), 1 ♀ (BFUS-TEN000081), 2 ♂♂ & 2 ♀♀ (IBER-BAS), in dead *Pinus sylvestris* tree, leg. V. Vassilev; E Rhodopes Mts, Sarta ridge, SE of Kobilino Vill., N41.493971° E26.013099°, 493 m a.s.l., 5–6.VII.2025, 1 ♀ (BFUS-TEN000082), at light, leg. O. Sivilov & V. Gashtarov.

Distribution: Albania, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria (new country record, see Fig. 4), Croatia (including Mljet), Czech Republic, Denmark (Bornholm, Sjælland), Estonia (including Hiiumaa), Finland (including Iso-Nauvo, Norstö, Ruissalo and some small islands), France (including Corsica), Georgia, Germany, Greece (including Corfu, Crete, Thasos), Hungary, Italy (including Sardinia), Kazakhstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Morocco, Norway (including Barmen [Aust-Agders], Jomfruland, Skåtøy, Tromøy and some small islands), Poland, Romania, Russia (from the Baltic region in the west to Primorsky Krai in the east), Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden (including Djursö, Gotland, Gotska Sandön, Öland, Vaddö, Yxnö and some small islands), Switzerland, Ukraine (Horion, 1956; Kühnelt, 1965; Kaszab, 1967; Kotomina & Sheshnitsan, 2010; Iwan et al., 2020; Nabozhenko & Ivanov, 2024; GBIF 2026d; Fowles, 2026; Naturbasen, 2026).

Notes: *Uloma rufa* is generally less common than *U. culinaris* in many countries (Reitter, 1911; Stebnicka, 1991; Merkl, 1998; Soldati, 2007;

Abdurakhmanov & Nabozhenko, 2011; Novák, 2014; Brůha et al., 2022), including Bulgaria (this record). This is a species with low population density (Kaszab, 1969; Nikitsky et al., 1996; Alekseev, 2008; Nikitsky, 2016; Bouget et al., 2019) but sometimes locally abundant (Bouget et al., 2019). It was listed as Endangered in the national Red Lists of Italy (Audisio et al., 2014) and Germany (Bense, 2002) but subsequently was downgraded to Near Threatened in Germany's Red List of threatened species (Schmidl et al., 2021). On the other hand, *U. rufa* is numerous and widespread in some European regions: Boronkamellék in Hungary, the Carpathians and Croatia (József, 1992); Poland (Iwan et al., 2012; Konwerski et al., 2024); Lot-et-Garonne and Corsica, France (Tamisier, 2005; Soldati, 2007); Zhytomyr Oblast, Ukraine (Andreieva et al., 2019); Upper Lusatia, Germany (Brůha et al., 2022). Horion (1956) considers it a boreo-montane species, but our data do not support this opinion as *U. rufa* was found in some warm lowland habitats in Bulgaria.

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Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the authors, reviewers, or subject editor.

Author' contributions

(using [CrediT](#))

Ognyan Sivilov: data curation, investigation, resources, visualisation, writing—original draft; Vassil Vassilev: investigation, resources, visualisation; Rostislav Bekchiev: investigation, resources; Maria

Naumova: funding acquisition, project administration; Hristina Hristova: investigation, writing—original draft.

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